

Ambiguity of Temperature as a Lagrange Multiplier for a Lorentz Boost

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In the literature (1), there are three well-known different prescriptions for the transformation of T , temperature, during a Lorentz boost. One suggests that $T_{\text{new}} = g T$ ($g = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$), the second that $T_{\text{new}} = T/g$ and the third, that $T_{\text{new}} = T$.

In this note, we consider the relativistic form of the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor (Jüttner distribution) which is based on independence of single particle energies for a fixed total energy. In such a case, the only information carried by a single particle is e . This allows for $f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4)$ for $e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4$ to yield: $\ln(f(e_i)) = e_i$. If one Lorentz boosts such a system, there is information about total energy and the boost velocity v_1 . Given that $f(e)$ is proportional to $\exp(-e/T)$, and $Nf(e)$ represents a number which does not change with a boost, if e_{new} maps 1-1 to e (non-boost), one may rewrite e in terms of e_{new} . This yields $e = e' / \{ g_1 (1-vv_1) \}$ where $g_1 = 1/\sqrt{1-v_1v_1/cc}$ and v is the non-boosted velocity. Then: $-e/T_{\text{old}} = -e' / \{ T_{\text{old}} g_1 (1-vv_1) \}$. Considering only parameters, one seems to have two choices. One might consider T_{old} to be the temperature in the boosted frame and g_1 a second collective parameter, or one might consider $T_{\text{old}} g_1$ to be the new temperature, so that all terms not explicitly related to single particle information are combined. An alternative way to obtain this result is to maximize entropy subject to two constraints, total energy and total momentum. In such a case, the Lagrange multipliers would absorb non-single particle information and $T_{\text{new}} = T_{\text{old}} g_1$.

We suggest that the ambiguity in the transformation of T in a Lorentz boost is already present in the example above. We also note that (1) deal with the ambiguity by considering different kinds of thermometers which measure different temperatures based on the details of the interaction of the thermometer with the system.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution and Information

We have argued in previous notes that the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution implies that the only information present is the single particle energy. The particles are independent. Thus, an interaction simply partitions the total energy with no bias whatsoever. Any $e_i + e_j = E_1$, must represent the same unnormalized probability $f(e_i)f(e_j)$ (independence). This leads to the unnormalized result:

$$f(e_i) = \exp(-e_i/T) \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{where } T \text{ is a parameter such that: } \sum \text{over } i \text{ } e_i f(e_i) C(T) = E/N \quad ((1b))$$

Here E is the total energy, N the number of particles and C a normalization constant.

The parameter T may also be thought of as being related to the Lagrange multiplier $1/T$ if one maximizes $\ln(\text{number of permutations of } n(e_i))$ subject to the constraint ((1b)).

If one has a nonrelativistic particle, then $e_i = pp/2m$, but for a relativistic situation with all particles having the same rest mass m_0 , $e_i = \sqrt{pp + m_0m_0}$, $c=1$.

We consider a gas of relativistic particles and ask: What temperature does one see from a frame moving with speed v_1 in the x direction?

Lorentz Boost and the Effect on Temperature

A Lorentz boost affects e and $p=ev$ ($c=1$) in the following way:

$$\begin{pmatrix} p' \\ e' \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} g_1 & -g_1 v_1 \\ -g_1 v_1 & g_1 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} p \\ e \end{pmatrix} \quad ((2))$$

$$E' = eg(1-vv_1) \quad ((3))$$

Given that $N f(e_i)$ represents the number of particles with energy e_i in the non-boosted frame, and number is an invariant, if e_i maps 1-1 to e_i' , then:

$$Nf(e_i) = N g(e_i', v) = N \exp\left(-\frac{e_i'}{T_{old} g_1 (1-vv_1)}\right) \quad ((4))$$

Here v is the speed in the non-boosted frame and v_1 is the velocity linked to the boost in the x -direction. One considers a gas moving in one dimension for simplicity.

We suggest that there is an ambiguity in temperature at this point. One seems to have two immediate choices:

- (A) One may let $T_{new} = T_{old}$. There is then a collective parameter g_1 which does not contain explicitly single particle information sitting by itself in ((4))
- (B) One may combine $T_{old} g_1 = T_{new}$ so that all collective parameters are associated in T_{new} . This suggests that T_{new} transforms as the fourth component of a 4-vector.

There is another way to consider (B). One may imagine maximizing entropy subject to two constraints in the moving frame, namely energy and total momentum. In the lab frame, one has a total energy E and $P=0$ so this 4-vector may be transformed using the matrix in ((2)). The maximization of entropy usually presents constraints in terms of single particle information only, i.e.

$$\text{Maximize : } \sum_i n(e_i') \ln(n(e_i')) + B_1 \sum_i e_i' n(e_i') + B_2 \sum_i p_i' n(e_i')$$

Here e_i' is the energy in the boosted frame and p_i' , the momentum in the boosted frame. This leads to the result:

$$n(e_i') = C \exp\{- [B_1 e_i' + B_2 p_i']\} \quad ((5))$$

In general, all information not related to single particle information is absorbed into the Lagrange multipliers in a maximization approach.

In this prescription, one may see that $1/T$ absorbs all non-single particle information, i.e. this is akin to $T_{\text{new}} = T_{\text{old}} g_1$.

{Note: $(E, P=0)$ transforms to: $E' = g_1 E$ and $P' = -v_1 g_1 E$

$P_i' = g_1(p_i - g_1 v_1 e_i)$ and $e_i' = g_1(-v_1 p_i + e_i)$ where $p_i = v_i e_i$ so $p_i' = e_i' (v_i - g_1 v_1) / (1 - v_1 v_i)$

This yields $\exp(- \{B_1 - B_1 v_1 v + B_2 v - B_2 g_1 v_1\} / (1 - v_1 v))$.

If $-B_1 v_1 v + B_2 v = 0$, then $B_1 = B_2 / v_1$. This seems to be consistent with:

$d/dB_1 \text{ Sum over } i \exp(- B_1 e_i' - B_2 p_i') = EC g_1$ and $d/dB_2 \text{ Sum over } i \exp(- B_1 e_i' - B_2 p_i') = EC g_1 v_1$

Here C is the normalization constant of the distribution. }

Approach of (1)

We note that in (1), the three possibilities $T_{\text{new}} = T_{\text{old}}$, $T_{\text{new}} = g_1 T_{\text{old}}$ and $T_{\text{new}} = T_{\text{old}} / g_1$ are considered as being due to three different types of thermometers. In particular, a thermometer is said to interact weakly with the system, yet there may still be different types of interactions for different physical thermometers leading to different T measurement values. $T_{\text{old}} = T_{\text{new}}$ suggests that T is a statistical property of the non-boosted frame. Thus, it retains its statistical measurable value in the boosted frame. One way to allow for this is to have the thermometer move with the boosted velocity of v_1 (2).

$g_1 T_{\text{old}}$ on the other hand transforms T as the fourth component of a 4-vector.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we examine the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution for relativistic particles (i.e. the Juttner distribution) and argue that in a boosted frame, if one treats T as a parameter (e.g. a Lagrange multiplier in a maximization of energy), one might tend to consider $T_{\text{new}} = g_1 T_{\text{old}}$ where $g_1 = 1/\sqrt{1 - v_1^2/c^2}$. Alternatively, one might leave $T_{\text{new}} = T_{\text{old}}$ and consider g_1 to be an extra collective parameter. As a result, we suggest that there is an ambiguity in choosing how T transforms.

References

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https://www.researchgate.net/publication/366903096_Covariant_Temperature_A_Brief_Review